
Assessing Apple's compliance with the
Digital Markets Act

The barriers against Device Neutrality

Free Software Foundation Europe

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Executive summary

This report lays down the assessment of Apple's updated [compliance plan](#) with the Digital Markets Act (DMA) launched in June, 2025, and the impact over "[Device Neutrality](#)" and Free Software in general. Since the compliance procedures are dynamic, the conclusions of this report are, therefore, provisional. **This paper do not configure legal/economic/business advice.**

Closer examination of Apple's plans reveals some fragilities in relation to DMA compliance. Apple's business terms introduce severe risks for developers and users' software freedom, tighter control over the Apps Store and increasing switching costs for users in relation to their personal data. This report concludes that, while the DMA aims to promote contestability and fairness, Apple's proposed changes **are still reinforcing** its monopolistic behaviour by restricting software freedom, strengthening the dependency of developers and users on its own services and products and increasing switching costs. The report also puts forth how integrity of operating system must not be used summarily for imposing restrictions on 3rd party app stores.

Besides underscoring the urgency to impose strict observance of DMA rules to the designated gatekeepers, this report also highlights the necessity to safeguard Device Neutrality in broader terms by promoting higher degrees of software freedom, weakening vendor and manufacturer lock ins and better policies for end-user control over data. Incorporating principles of device neutrality by default in their operations would be a crucial step in this direction.

Glossary

"App store": An entity that provides services for mobile application ingestion, review, and distribution.

"Breaking" iPhone: Somehow similar to the term "rooting" on Android systems, "breaking" (sometimes also commonly referred as "jailbreaking") relates to users bypassing the built-in restrictions on iPhones. to download and install For example it lets users install unsigned apps on iPhones. of an android phone.

(3PAS): "3rd-party app store" understand app store service run by a non-Apple organization. Apple refers to these as *"Alternative app marketplaces."*

(3PASA): "3rd-party app store app" the actual program, approved by Apple and available for side-loading via direct download (e.g, from a web page), that enables users to download and install apps provided by the 3PAS.

(AAS): "Apple App Store": The app store service run by Apple Inc.

(AASA): "Apple App Store app": The actual program, pre-installed on all iOS devices, that enables users to download and install Apple-approved apps.

(ASC): „App Store Connect“: Apple’s online services for ingesting, reviewing and distributing applications for their app stores.

DMA: Digital Markets Act

EC: European Commission

ECJ: European Court of Justice

EU Charter: Charter of fundamental rights of the European Union

FSFE: Free Software Foundation Europe

Notarization in iOS: A complete security and policy review of apps by Apple, and a subsequent re-signed and encrypted binary with proprietary DRM, which iOS requires in order to be allowed to install.

Side-loading: The act of installing a program on a device directly, either from the Internet or other means, without going through an App store.

Introduction

The FSFE deeply appreciates the opportunity to present its opinion to the European Commission on Apple's new strategy to comply with DMA and its impact on Free Software (also known as Open Source Software).

The FSFE has a 20-years expertise working with competition law matters. Besides being involved with strategic litigation in Europe ([Microsoft case](#)), the organisation was involved in the Digital Markets Act (DMA) legislative process as a stakeholder reporting the impact of the law on Free Software. The FSFE has also worked with competition and telecommunications regulators all over Europe in the topics related to [digital devices and Free Software](#). We are happy and honoured to collaborate with the European commission (EC).

The dominant power of corporations like Apple over digital devices has sparked policy, regulatory, and legal reactions trying to impose accountability on such large enterprises controlling how end-users should use their equipment. The DMA addresses companies exercising control over whole platform ecosystems in the digital economy and are structurally extremely difficult to challenge or contest by existing or new market operators, irrespective of how innovative and efficient those market operators may be (Recital 3).

In September 2023, the [European Commission \(EC\) has designated Apple as gatekeeper](#) under Art. 3 DMA by determining the following services as gateway for business users to reach end users: (i) Apple's online intermediation service App Store; (ii) Apple's operating system iOS; and (iii) Apple's web browser Safari.¹

In regards to this decision, Apple endeavoured two approaches: the company appealed of the EC's decision in December, 2023 to the European Court of Justice (ECJ) ([T-1080/23](#)), and [announced in January, 2024, then in June, 2025 changes to iOS, Safari and the App Store to comply with the DMA. Apple repeatedly updated the new terms and conditions.](#) The proposed changes commenced with the iOS 17.4 version. This report will focus on App Store and iOS.

¹ On 29 April 2024, based on the findings of a market investigation, [the EC also designated Apple as gatekeeper with respect to its iPadOS.](#)

Closer examination of new Apple's plans **still reveal** some fragilities in relation to DMA compliance, and the introduction of severe risks for developers and users' software freedom, tighter control over the App Store and increasing switching costs for users in relation to their personal data. This report concludes that, while the DMA aims to promote contestability and fairness, Apple's terms for alternative app distribution reinforce its monopolistic behaviours by restricting software freedom, strengthening the dependency of developers and users to its own services and products and increasing switching costs. The report also puts forth how integrity of operating system must not be used summarily for imposing restrictions on 3rd party app stores.

Besides underscoring the urgency to impose strict observance of DMA rules to the designated gatekeepers, this report also highlights the necessity to safeguard Device Neutrality in broader terms by promoting higher degrees of software freedom, weakening vendor and manufacturer lock ins and better policies for end-user control over data.

This reports concludes with a set of recommendations aimed at Apple's plans for DMA compliance from the interests of Free Software developers and users.

Apple's online intermediation service App Store

Apple exercises a tight-knitted centralized control over the app store infrastructure. Apple operates its App Store as a unified digital store front across various platforms, including:

- App Store on iPhones ("iOS App Store");
- App Store on iPads ("iPadOS App Store");
- App Store on Mac computers ("Mac App Store");
- App Store on Apple TVs ("tvOS App Store"); and
- App Store on Apple Watches ("watchOS App Store").

While Apple affirms that each of its five app stores constitutes a distinct CPS under the DMA, the FSFE is of the opinion (similarly to that of EC) that while there are nuances in the application availability and functionality across these platforms, - the underlying structure and governance are consistent, representing a single, integrated ecosystem rather than distinct app stores for each platform:

- (a) the App Store is used for the same purpose from both an end user and a business user perspective across all devices on which it is available, namely to intermediate the distribution of applications.

- (b) Apple provides a common framework of agreements governing Apple's legal relationship with app developers, such as the Apple Developer Program License Agreement and the Apple Developer Agreement. These agreements apply to all of Apple's app developers, regardless of the device and operating system on which they distribute their apps.
- (c) Apple's documentation regarding policies, agreements and guidelines apply across devices, for instance:
 - (a) the agreement on the use of application development tools, in particular the Xcode and SDKs Agreement. This agreement contains a reference to the distribution of apps developed for specific operating systems through the (single) App Store;
 - (b) the privacy policy to app developers;
 - (c) the advertising policies applicable on the App Store;
 - (d) "Marketing and Identity Guidelines", and others.
 - (e) iPadOS is the same as the iOS in terms of the software that runs the operating system. The iOS and iPadOS distinction is purely a marketing one, not technical. Apps created for iOS are automatically configured to run on iPadOS.
 - (f) While the DMA is compelling Apple to allow alternative app stores, the company is trying to maintain a significant level of control over its ecosystem. The new changes are made to look undesirable to make developers and users stick to the status quo in several ways, reinforcing Apple's gatekeeping position.

Apple's terms for alternative app distribution

A closer examination of the [press release](#) and [Apple's developers support page updates](#) reveal that requirements the alternative app store developers will have to meet are **still** undesirable and unreasonably extensive. In this section we focus on the terms for alternative app distribution introduced by Apple and its potential non-conformity with DMA.

The new terms announced in July 2025 only apply for the communication and promotion of offers. It is still unclear how the Core Technology Fee will be replaced by the Core Technology Commission for what concerns alternative app distribution. The terms for alternative app distribution are still the same and are set in the so called "Alternative Terms Addendum for Apps in the EU" to the Apple Developer Program License Agreement.

Changes proposed by Apple for iOS 17.4 in relation to third-party app stores²

#	Apple iPhone App Store (Current System)	Alternative iPhone App Marketplaces (New)	Android 3rd-party apps stores [Comparison]
1	Developers register with Apple, T&Cs, \$99/year	Developers register with Apple, T&Cs, \$99/year	No Google developer registration requirement. However, from 2027, Google will require developers to verify their identity to distribute ap via the Web.³
2	Mandatory app review for functionality, security, policy, content	Mandatory app review for functionality & security	Google lets users select which review from the device itself
3	Apps ingested through App Store Connect and encrypted with DRM	Apps ingested through App Store Connect and encrypted with DRM	No DRM or encryption applied to apps
4	Apps distributed via Apple App Store only	Apps distributed via Apple App Store or a 3 rd party app store which must be based in EU and provide annual €1M letter of credit (or) have been an Apple developer program member for two years and have an app that has been downloaded 1M times in the EU in the previous year.	Apps distributed via Google Play Store, Samsung Store, Amazon Store, F-Droid, etc.
5	No side-loading	No side-loading, with the sole exception of Apple-approved 3rd party app store apps themselves or the Apple authorized developer's website; Apps must either be installed through 3rd party app store apps, Apple App store or Apple authorized developer website.	Side-loading permitted by direct download of .apk from any source. However, from 2027, Google will require developers to verify their identity to distribute ap via the Web⁴.
6	30% commission on all digital commerce	€0.50/install Core Technology Fee	No fee for downloads or commission on digital

² Table retrieved from: Prud'hommeaux, Marc. *iPhone App Marketplaces Changes proposed by Apple for iOS 17.4*. Presentation slides on the App Fair Project. 12.02.2024.

³ <https://arstechnica.com/gadgets/2025/08/google-will-block-sideloadng-of-unverified-android-apps-starting-next-year/>

⁴ <https://arstechnica.com/gadgets/2025/08/google-will-block-sideloadng-of-unverified-android-apps-starting-next-year/>

Discrimination via terms and conditions (#1 and #6)

Apples' pricing and fees policies discriminately affect Free Software projects due to the disproportional burden over projects that aim to enter the iOS environment to make use of the hardware as general purpose computer. [Apple Developer Program](#) still represents a considerable barrier for third party developers wanting to distribute apps for Apple devices, and impacts fairness in two ways:

- the imposition of Apple tools for app development; and
- the yearly fee represent unduly discrimination towards smaller FOSS developers that do not possess the capacity to scale to meet such requirements.

The Free Software 3rd party app stores/repositories are potential competitors to Apple's App store and therefore must be viewed in that sense. Apple's new terms in an effort to comply with the DMA fall short of contestability and fairness requirements that form the basis of DMA and thereby block entry and innovation. Fairness and contestability are interlinked as per recital 34 of the DMA. Fairness cannot be maintained if there is no contestability and vice versa. [Academic research](#) understands fairness under the DMA as follows;

- *Fairness in Surplus Sharing:* Dominant platforms can extract a significant proportion of surplus from their presence in the market, often far exceeding their contribution to society's welfare. This is due to network effects and economies of scale, which limit competition and allow platforms to charge high prices or extract surplus from users. In the case of Apple, the FSFE submits that, its strict control over the App Store and imposition of fees on third-party app distribution could be seen as unfairly restricting the ability of developers and users to share in the surplus generated by the platform. FSFE therefore believes that opening up the ecosystem to alternative distribution channels would allow for fairer competition and more equitable distribution of surplus.
- *Fairness of Contractual Terms:* Protecting users from unfair clauses in standard contracts. In the case of Apple's non-negotiable App Store policies, developers are subject to strict terms and conditions imposed by Apple, including hefty fees for distribution and restrictions on side-loading. FSFE submits that developers should have more flexibility in choosing how to distribute their software and that users should not be locked into a single distribution channel controlled by Apple.

- *Fairness in Processes and Practices*: This emphasizes the importance of fairness in the design and enforcement of platform rules, particularly for dominant platforms acting as "private regulators." FSFE believes that Apple's control over the App Store ecosystem, including its approval process for apps and enforcement of DRM encryption are limiting developers' and users' freedom and hindering fair competition.

In the previous terms, Apple charged 30% commission on all digital commerce within the companies' ecosystem. Apple has introduced several smaller fees,⁵ including the "core technology fee", which will disproportionately affect those app developers that have limited revenues, but whose apps are widely downloaded. These commissions are not fair and reasonable and are not compliant with Art. 6(12), (13) and recital 52 DMA.

In its latest announcement, Apple confirmed that the CTF will be replaced by the Core Technology Commission (CTC). However, at present, the CTC appears to apply only to the communication and promotion of offers. It remains unclear whether the CTF will be eliminated entirely or replaced with another type of fee. Meanwhile, the existing obligations for alternative app distribution remain in force, alongside additional requirements such as the €1 million letter of credit and the download thresholds. These measures continue to place a disproportionate burden on Free Software and raise concerns about Apple's potentially anti-competitive and non-compliant practices.

Free Software 3rd party app stores or repositories have the potential to compete with the Apple App store but are being restricted by Apple's gatekeeper control and practices. They compete with AAS not by scale but in principles i.e for example, by offering curated app stores and repositories that can cater to a specific community's interests or user's interests.

Free Software 3rd party app stores cannot function around the current terms by Apple, which means that the DMA objectives of fairness and contestability may not be realized. The FSFE understands that DMA's goals require the ability for 3rd party app stores to emerge and function as competitors on smartphones. Apple's fee effectively undermines the objectives of the DMA by rendering the introduction of 3rd party app stores economically impractical, as they are unable

⁵ "App Store apps will be subject to a reduced commission rate of either 17% on transactions for digital goods and services, or 10% (for the vast majority of developers and subscriptions after their first year), irrespective of the payment processing system chosen". "Payment processing fee — For an additional 3%, iOS applications available on the App Store may utilise the App Store's payment processing". Apple does not charge developers any additional fees when they link consumers to a website or utilise a Payment Service Provider within their application to process payments.

to attract popular apps. Apple's new business terms adopting this contract when it is confronted with competition appears to be an example of anticompetitive behaviour. Apple justifies the Core Technology Fees and the commission with the value it provides to the developers. However, the developers and users provide Apple with greater value and therefore must [benefit fairly](#) from Apple with greater choice and fair marketing conditions.

For instance, let's assume *XCP*, a 3rd party app store dedicated to curated Free Software applications for users interested in such offerings. *XCP* would naturally be motivated to tap into the iOS ecosystem to reach iPhone users keen on Free Software apps. Now, suppose a popular Free Software iOS app called *MCP* wishes to reach users through the *XCP* Free Software store. In this scenario, *MCP* must adhere to Apple's new terms. As *MCP* begins distributing its app via the *XCP* store, it will incur a charge of €0.50 for each user (after the initial one million) it serves through both the Apple App Store and the *XCP* store. In that case, popular apps with high users like *MCP* will be reluctant to distribute their app on 3rd party app stores fearing heavy fees. Hence, Apple summarily [taxed its competitors entry](#) and this will be hugely detrimental to the Free Software 3rd party app stores.

The “core technology fee” is unreasonable, arbitrary and exploitative. [Several estimates](#) using [Apple's fee calculator](#) show that if there is an app with 10 million sales then Apple takes a 6.2 million cut in the sales. This amounts to 515,942 per month compared to 250,000 per month and 3 million per annum under the status quo. The screenshot below demonstrates Apple's new fee policies that have a negative impact on the developers.

Fee calculator
Estimate how the different models may apply to your business on iOS in the EU.

Do you sell digital goods and services in your iOS app or game? [Learn more >](#)

How much in annual sales do you expect your app or game to make per year through the App Store on iOS from digital goods and services sold in the EU?
Reference your 2023 data in Sales and Trends to help estimate this number. [Learn more >](#)

Are you a member of the App Store Small Business Program?

How many first annual installs do you expect your app or game to generate per year in the EU?
Each app receives one million first annual installs per year at no cost. Reference your 2023 data in Sales and Trends to help estimate this number. [Learn more >](#)

Select an option to view results:

Select an option

Selected
App Store with IAP

Estimated monthly fees

App Store commission
\$ 83,333

App Store payment processing
\$ 25,000

Core Technology Fee
\$ 407,609

Total monthly fees
\$ 515,942

Dollars | Euros

Retrieved from apple website [Fee calculator](#)

Gatekeeper control via app review (#2)

Apple exercises a tight control over app review. While Apple has conducted review for functionality, security, policy, content, in the new terms the company has reduced the parameters for functionality and security. App review can be considered a legitimised curation activity by app stores and marketplaces. However, some review parameters can cause self-preference and discrimination when the same attitude is not equally applied to the same type of app.

No Side-loading (#3 and #5)

As with the previous terms, Apple **still** does not allow side-loading. The sole exception is Apple-approved 3rd party app store apps themselves or developer's website; every other app must either be installed either through one of these 3rd party app store apps, or through the Apple App Store app.⁶ Developers who do not actively choose to accept Apple's new business terms, which took effect in March 2024 (they can agree to the terms at any time, as per Apple's policy), **are** automatically and technically prevented from distributing apps in app stores that are not native to Apple. According to Art. 6(4) DMA, Apple is required to permit side-loading. However, Apple is interpreting this requirement very narrowly.

As comparison, side-loading is still available on personal computers, including Macs. Apple argues that the introduction of side-loading in the EU under the DMA will lead to a less secure system compared to the current model in the rest of the world. Apple uses this as a justification to implement various controls that will make their obligations under Article 6(4) DMA less clear. Apps will need to undergo Apple's full app review, and then be "[notarized](#)" - packaged, and encrypted with proprietary DRM encryption regardless of how they are distributed. Apple exercises gatekeeper control on how an app is submitted to the Apple App Store and further distributed to the public. Any app developed for the App Store must be ingested through [App Store Connect \(ASC\)](#) and encrypted with Apple's proprietary DRM. The, the app's binary is provided in a encrypted manner via the App Store to the public. This system behaves identically regardless of whether the app is distributed through Apple's App store or a 3rd party app store.

⁶ [Distributing directly from developers' website](#) web distribution is available with a software update. It will let Apple authorized developers distribute their iOS apps to EU users directly

Apple's approach leads to extreme forms of control and consolidates its entrenched position of gatekeeper over its devices.

By forcing proprietary encryption via DRM over the submitted code, it is not possible to further audit the app's source code, since a credible reproducible build of the app is no longer possible. This has serious implications towards security – as third party auditors cannot certify the authenticity of the source code -, and to software freedom, as users are not allowed to check the source code of free and open source software without breaking Apple's DRM.

Narrow enablement of 3rd-party app stores (#4)

With the current terms, 3rd party app stores and repositories (3PAS) will be allowed by Apple. However, Apple implements this DMA-related obligation very narrowly, and continues to exercise unreasonable control, such as requiring a 1 million euro letter of credit per year or two year past membership with Apple developer program with an app download count of 1 Million. In comparison, in the Android ecosystem, apps can be distributed not only via Google Play Store but also another 3rd party app stores.

Apple will only grant 3rd party app store developers the ability to establish 3rd party app stores or repositories (3PAS), provided that they undertake substantial accountability and supervision regarding user experience while administering the said app stores. By retaining its control to grant app store developers permission to distribute specialized app stores for iOS apps, provided they satisfy particular requirements and commit to upholding ongoing criteria for safeguarding users and developers (referred to as Alternative App Marketplace Entitlement process). The developers of 3PAs will be accountable for the operation of their application stores, which appears to be reasonable. In addition, Apple will grant authorization to 3PAS developers who can provide a letter of credit from an A-rated financial institution in the amount of €1,000,000, with an annual renewal requirement. This immediately puts 3PAS developers at a huge disadvantage simply because it is a huge number and obtaining this letter of credit is not feasible for all the 3rd party app store developers.

Besides, according to these new business terms, the marketplace developers will be charged by Apple 0,50€ for each first annual install of their marketplace app above the 1MM threshold generated from the App store. Apple calls this a 'Core Technology Fee' (CTF). Shockingly, the 1MM free first annual thresholds are not available for 3rd party app store apps and so they will pay the CTF for every first annual install of the app, including installs that occur before the 1 million threshold is met. The definition of 'first annual install' is broad and vague. It includes the first installation of an app, as well as subsequent installations or

updates from any iOS app distribution method within a 12-month time frame. So a developer would have to pay this fee even if a user downloaded the app, never used it and forgot to delete it.

The broad interpretation of first annual installations penalises developers who have a substantial number of existing users/limited number of users and undermines their motivation to release feature updates. Moreover, the stipulation that CTF is priced per install creates an obstacle for 3rd party app store (3PAS) developers to achieve the necessary scope to compete with Apple's proprietary App Store on merit.

Summary flowchart for app stores

The summary of the new terms and how they affect software freedom by increasing vendor lock-in and switching costs are given in the flowchart below.

Apple's Gatekeeper control and the DMA

iOS interoperability, 3rd party apps/stores, and integrity issues: hurdles for Free Software under the guise of security and integrity of OS

Issues with security

The DMA is introducing new interoperability rules that will apply to Apple's operating systems including iOS. The company offers five distinct operating systems. The interoperability rules referred here are laid down in Art.6 (7) DMA. The objective is to promote interoperability which is an already established concept under the [European directive for electronic communications](#). Interoperability allows for freedom of choice for users/consumers and improves interconnectivity within the internal market and thereby upholds consumer protection as per [Art.38 of the EU Charter](#). In order to achieve the above-mentioned set goals it is genuinely necessary to restrict the gatekeeper's dominant positions in the relevant market and mandate for interoperable standards.

On the other hand, Integrity of the hardware or the operating system according to recital 50 of the DMA refers to

*“design options that need to be implemented and maintained in order for the hardware or the operating system to be protected against unauthorised access, by ensuring that security controls specified for the hardware or the operating system concerned cannot be compromised.. Furthermore, in order to ensure that third-party software applications or software application stores do not undermine end users' security, it should be possible for the gatekeeper to implement **strictly necessary and proportionate measures and settings**, other than default settings, enabling end users to effectively protect security in relation to third-party software applications or software application stores if the gatekeeper demonstrates that such measures and settings are strictly necessary and justified and that there are no less-restrictive means to achieve that goal.”*

Art. 6(4) of the DMA allows Apple to take only strictly necessary and proportionate measures to ensure that the 3rd party apps and app stores do not endanger the integrity of its hardware and operating system. Apple must also duly justify these measures it incorporated.

Apple is summarily claiming that all the 3rd party app stores and apps will endanger the integrity of iOS operating system. Apple therefore is effectively blocking competition using security and integrity claims without any valid

justifications. Apple unduly believes that allowing 3rd party app stores and alternative distribution of apps would pose a significant risk to the integrity and security of its iOS operating system. Hence, Apple justifies the hefty fees structure and “notarization”.

However, Apple does not impose such terms with their Mac desktops and laptops. In MacOS, Apple removes the need for developers to pay to have their software sold through an app store that is controlled by Apple. Instead, developers can sell their product directly to Mac users. Despite this, Mac users are still protected, showing that Apple's regulations regarding the iPhone app store are far more restrictive than needed to ensure customers' safety and privacy.

Conversely, the claims by the company that concentrated control would enhance security by posing iPhone [most secure smart phone option in the EU and most secure mobile computing platform in the world](#) are problematic. There have been several instances of [severe security breaches](#) within the Apple App Store, along with mounting evidence suggesting [Apple App Store mishandling privacy of users, have been brought to light in the US courts](#). Apple App Store too, with its centralized control over security and privacy, poses a risk to the security and privacy of the users. Centralized control means a single point of failure may result in compromising the system integrity.

Issues with integrity

In this context, it is important to understand the meaning and intent behind the term ‘integrity’. In the case of [Microsoft vs the commission](#), integrity of the operating system was interpreted as something vital and irreplaceable for the overall functioning. In that occasion, the court rejected Microsoft’s argument that integrating a media player into the operating system was vital for the integrity of the system. Integrity, therefore, meant protective design options needed against unauthorised access.

In light of that, the FSFE, submits that Apple retaining tight control over its ecosystem does not protect its integrity. In order to ensure fairness face the arguments of integrity of operating system v/s 3rd party app stores/apps must be assessed in the following ways:

- **Whether the users have the ability to modify or remove specific components without significantly impacting overall functionality of the OS.** Apple iOS operating system can function seamlessly with 3rd party app store apps and 3rd party apps. By blocking 3rd party app stores and side-loading, Apple limits user choice and restricts access to alternative software distribution channels. However, this restriction does not necessarily enhance or protect integrity of the iOS operating system itself,

but rather limits user freedom without a clear justification tied to system integrity or security.

- **Whether technical distinctions between different components within the software architecture ensure overall system coherence and functionality.** This indicates a nuanced understanding of the operating system's architecture and functionality, where certain components can be differentiated without compromising the overall integrity or functionality of the system. Apple's iPhone can technically function in the absence of Apple App store and in the presence of 3rd party apps. However, due to Apple's vendor lock-in, it is not possible to install any apps or updates outside the Apple App store which is the sole place to get apps on iOS. Users sometimes break the built-in restrictions on iPhones to install unsigned apps. This results in the termination of the Apple warranty. However, iPhone still functions as a smartphone. This establishes that the co-existence of 3rd party app stores and apps with Apple App store do not impact the functionality and integrity of the iPhone and iOS.
- **Whether the inclusion or exclusion of specific components does not unduly restrict developer innovation or user freedom.** Apple fails to duly justify how "notarization" for 3rd party app stores, DRM encryption, and strict eligibility criteria for 3rd party app stores are necessary for protecting the integrity of iOS operating system. Instead, Apple is impeding the developers' freedom to innovate and utilize various tools without being constrained by the presence or absence of specific components within the operating system. It is pertinent to note that Apple offers sideloadable [Apple Music \(applemusic.apk file\) for Android](#), but Apple does not permit the same direct side-loading of, say, `spotify.ipa` for Apple devices. This is inconsistent with their claims of Apple devices being the most secure. This poses the question: *Why would Apple expose their Apple Music users to any fundamental insecurities that come along with side-loading?*

iOS Interoperability and security standards

Apple has opted to establish a [request form](#) for enabling interoperability with iOS and iPhone features on a case-by-case basis. Although having a clear form for contacting Apple in topics regarding interoperability is a welcoming progress, the FSFE considers the way the company is proposing to manage interoperability requests may violate DMA by the following:

- The interoperability grant referred in Art.6(7) is completely different from Art.7(1) and does not require any form of request. Art.6(7) is clear in the sense that gatekeepers *"shall allow providers of services and providers of*

hardware, free of charge, effective interoperability". Interoperability should be granted automatically, and only in very narrow exceptions could be reasonably and proportionarily limited. Currently, the company has complete control on how and when to grant interoperability, contrary to what the law requires.

- The management of granting or denying interoperability is vague regarding the decision making, as well as without a clear timeframe of when such requests should be resolved and disposed. Free Software projects have reported that they have waited weeks for a response on interoperability requests, directly impacting their competitiveness in iOS.
- Apple's arbitrary decision making regarding interoperability may lead to discriminatory practices and may create self-preferencing to Apple's services or affiliates. Without proper external audit, it is not possible to determine whether the reasons for denying interoperability are reasonable and strictly necessary according to the law.
- There is no appealing process in case a user is aggrieved by the decision of Apple. This shows that the procedure is arbitrary and gives Apple the power to summarily reject interoperability requests. Apple's request form for interoperability therefore creates additional hectic bureaucracy for developers and makes the access to interoperability highly difficult. Instead, Apple must disclose the procedure for decision making under this interoperability request form.
- Apple unduly believes that interoperability will compromise the system integrity and security.

The rationale for supporting the interoperability mandate in the DMA is that its implementation would not compromise existing user security standards and would not infringe upon the EU Charter's protections for privacy and personal data. The reasonable level of security while keeping the interoperability mandates is that it can lead to increased competition and innovation in the messaging service market. By allowing users on different platforms to communicate with each other, it breaks down the barriers that currently exist and promotes a more open and competitive environment.

This can incentivize service providers to improve their security measures in order to attract and retain users. With more users having the ability to choose their preferred messaging service, providers will have to prioritize security to gain a competitive edge. Additionally, interoperability can also lead to collaboration between service providers in addressing security challenges and sharing best practices. By working together, they can develop more robust security protocols and ensure that user data is protected across different platforms. Competition on

trustworthiness is key for consumer welfare. Users should have the freedom to make decisions about their privacy settings and weigh the trade-offs between privacy, security, and utility. Allowing users to choose better security providers enables them to customize their experience according to their preferences and needs.

Therefore, we are of the opinion that Apple's "interoperability request form" will consolidate Apple's gatekeeper control over the ecosystem, heavily discriminating against 3rd party apps and with the risk of self-preferencing its own solutions. Apple's decision making in regards to interoperability should be improved by:

- APIs' specifications should be made public and changes on it should have adequate buffer periods for developers to adapt. Access to systems functionalities should be facilitated, so developers can understand easily the feasibility of the provided APIs.
- Interoperability grants for the purpose of Art. 6(7) should happen automatically and be limited only by exceptional cases regarding strictly necessary measures regarding security and integrity.
- Apple's decision making in denying interoperability grants should be bound to a due process, including appealing procedures and external review and audit.
- Interoperability-related issues should be treated with high priority by Apple, and denial/granting decision should not be unduly delayed.

FSFE's demands: a claim for Device Neutrality

Gatekeepers with monopolistic behavior impede software freedom, trap end-users in lock-ins, and hinder personal control over data. Besides the negative effects on market competition, they negatively impact consumer welfare and digital sovereignty. At the heart of this issue lies the restriction on users' ability to freely install, run, and uninstall software on their devices, primarily motivated by commercial interests rather than security or privacy concerns. The FSFE runs the EU-wide initiative "[Device Neutrality & Free Software](#)" to raise awareness for policy topics regarding Free Software usage on devices, including the provisions of the DMA.

Apple's reaction to the DMA made the terms and conditions of Apple's App Store even worse than before. The revised pricing structure should not negatively impact the competitive dynamics of the ecosystem for developers, specifically for business users. Should Apple's refined cost structure negatively affect developers and force them to comply with existing business terms, the DMA will not

effectively balance the competitive landscape in both the upstream and downstream aspects of app distribution.

While the DMA marks progress towards fairness and competition in digital markets, the FSFE believes it is not enough. To truly achieve greater openness and equality, significant reforms in the business practices of large corporations like Apple, acting as gatekeepers, are necessary. Incorporating principles of device neutrality by default in their operations would be a crucial step in this direction.

Higher degrees of software freedom, no lock-in and lower switching costs

- **iPhone and iPad are general purpose computers.** Apple should not limit business and end-users in their software freedom by overstating arguments of integrity and security of devices. The co-existence of alternative app stores and alternative software installation (side-loading) do not present a serious risk for integrity per se.
- **No discrimination.** Apple should enable business and end-users to install 3rd party app stores without financial and technological hurdles. Apple should not impose fees for app installs/updates. Apple should not be allowed to impose residency or credit requirements for establishing 3rd party app stores or marketplaces.
- **Complete installation and uninstallation of software.** Apple should enable complete and unfettered third-party software installation (side-loading) without the DRM-based encryption system for distribution.
- **No DRM-based “notarization”.** Apple should not be allowed to control app ingest and further distribution via DRM encryption.
- **End-user control over app review.** Apple should allow users to select the type of app review from the device itself.
- **Effective interoperability.** Apple should not be allowed to impose arbitrary interoperability request forms, but interoperability should be granted automatically and effectively. APIs’ specifications should be made public and developers should have easy access to them. Apple must clearly disclose the details of the decision making process. In addition, a public timeline must be set up by Apple for managing the interoperability requests. Right to appeal must be provided by default for aggrieved parties. The appeal process must also be conducted in a transparent manner with a timeline and number of requests and appeals.

- **More competition.** Apple should compete on trustworthiness and let users choose their security and privacy providers.

Further information

[Device Neutrality and Free Software](#)